

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: STANLEY****FIRST NAME: RORY****PROGRAM CODE: DGEP****COURSE CODE : ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 6****INSTRUCTOR: DR. GULMA**

Edit or delete text to show actual information below:

The author applied US conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics

The author did *not* use Zotero to insert references

The author did Grammarly Premium (provided by EUCLID)

My plagiarism rate (per Grammarly Premium) is: 1%

The author used the following software: (MSWord 2016 on Windows 8)

QUIZ FOR COURSE ACA-401D

1. What are the dangers of using direct quotations?
 - Direct quotations can introduce unnecessary bias in analytical papers.
 - The use of direct quotations demonstrates that the writer cannot think for themselves.
 - If you utilize direct quotations too often, it does not appear as if you have done your own research.¹**
 - Direct quotations should only be used from primary sources.
2. When making a plan to write a paper, what are the critical components that should be included before you start writing?

¹ Laurent Cleenewerck and Kabiru Gulma. *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1, 4th ed.* (Bangui: Euclid University, 2021), 36.

- The plan should only include a list of primary sources that you will use to structure your paper around.
 - Your plan should have an answer to the question you are attempting to answer so you will be able to guide your research to find the information you need to support your solution throughout the paper.²**
 - Your plan should have a breakdown of the source material you expect to explore.
 - Your plan should integrate conversations with academic experts in the field you are writing about.
3. What should be included in the introduction of a paper?
- The introduction should provide a detailed accounting of all the sources that will be used to support the thesis.
 - The introduction should acknowledge the academic work that has already been performed in the particular field of study while also providing a detailed structure of the paper and a brief overview of the recommendations that will be provided throughout.
 - The introduction should tell the reader what the paper will cover while also covering the format and citation style that will be utilized throughout.
 - The introduction should include a brief overview of the topic being covered to orientate the reader and must answer the question presented with a thesis.³**

² Cleenewerck and Gulma, *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1*, 9.

³ Cleenewerck and Gulma, *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1*, 10.

4. What are the basics of research?

- The basics of research the paper research process is the survey of information for personal edification.
- The basics of research the paper research process is to determine the validity of other academic research conducted in the same field you are surveying
- The basics of the paper research process are answering a question by obtaining information.⁴**
- The basics of research the paper research process is to contribute to a particular academic field.

5. What is a good strategy to ensure clear concise and creative writing?

- Writing with music will ensure an individual's ability to write clearly and enhance creative thought.
- Keeping writing sessions manageable will ensure an individual's ability to write clearly and enhance creative thought.⁵**
- Ensuring writing sessions occur after a meal will ensure an individual's ability to write clearly and enhance creative thought.
- Writing immediately after conducting long periods of research will ensure an individual's ability to write clearly and enhance creative thought.

⁴ Kate Turabian, *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations: Chicago Style for Students and Researchers* (Chicago: The University of Chicago Press, 2018), 20.

⁵ Turabian, et al., *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations: Chicago Style for Students and Researchers*, 76.

6. What percentage of students never finish a dissertation?
- About 30 percent of students do not finish their dissertation.⁶**
 - About 40 percent finish their dissertation but only 30 percent are approved so approximately 70 percent never finish their dissertations.
 - Only about 8 percent of students do not finish their dissertations.
 - 80 percent of all students finish their dissertations.
7. What components should be included in a dissertation's first chapter?
- The first chapter should include a meaningful description of the purpose of the dissertation, a detailed review of the research process, and an outline of the dissertation.
 - The first chapter of the dissertation should only be dedicated to the research problem.
 - The summary and a short description of each portion, including the introduction, problem statement, statement of purpose, research questions, an overview of research design, rationale, and significance, the role of the researcher, researcher assumptions, the definition of key terminology, and organization of the dissertation.⁷**
 - The first chapter of the dissertation only needs to discuss the thesis and provide a literature review that will be used to explore the thesis.

⁶ Linda Bloomberg and Marie Volpe, *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation: A Roadmap from Beginning to End*. (Los Angeles: SAGE Publications, 2019), 333.

⁷ Bloomberg and Volpe, *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation: A Roadmap from Beginning to End*, 74-75.

8. What is the difference between Primary and Secondary Legislation?
- Primary legislation refers to the legislation that is enacted by the European Parliament and secondary legislation refers to executive directives issued by the European Commission.
 - Primary legislation is governed under Articles 294 and 289 while secondary legislation only applies to the Court of Justice.
 - The Court of Justice of the European Union has the sole authority to determine the difference between primary and secondary legislation.
 - Primary legislation refers to the governing treaties that governed the European Communities, eventually becoming the European Union. The European Coal and Steel Community, the European Economic Community, and the Euratom Treaty were the original treaties. Secondary legislation refers to the legislation or acts that are adopted under the legal basis established by the treaties. Article 288 of the Treaty on the Function of the European Union further explains and defines what qualifies as secondary legislation.⁸**

⁸ Tim Cooper, *English Style Guide: A Handbook for Authors and Translators in the European Commission*, eds. Daniel Alexander, Lorence Astwood, Kevin Birdseye, Tania Buhr, Mireille Cayley, Richard Davies, Gelen Dobby, Margaret Dolley, Alastair Ferguson, Angus Forsyth, Minna Helminen, Kara Lundsdatter, Daniel Marcus, Patrick McCarthy, Geraldine McKenna, Mark Osborne, Zornista Stoyanova-Yerburgh, Rebecca Watts (European Union, 2021), 72-77.

9. Beyond preventing plagiarism, what purpose does citation serve for the research field?

- To help others expand in the same field, we are all working together to improve.⁹**
- Demonstrates the writer's ability to conduct research.
- It can aid those who have been cited to gain notoriety in the academic field.
- Demonstrates the writer's ability to correctly use proper citation methods.

10. In order for a student to set themselves up to write a successful dissertation, what initial step must be taken?

- The student must develop a schedule that they can adhere to on a daily basis.
- The researcher must focus on selecting a question that is actually researchable.¹⁰**
- The student should come up with various potential topics and categorize them based on interest level and academic suitability.
- The student should determine if the topic they have selected will contribute to existing research.

⁹ Turabian, et al., *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations: Chicago Style for Students and Researchers*, 140.

¹⁰ Bloomberg and Volpe, *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation: A Roadmap from Beginning to End*, 242.

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Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Abubakar Gulma. 2025. ACA-401/ACA 401D Course Pack: Period 1. 6th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15245536>.